

Disease resistance of some promising rice cultivars

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Bacterial blight (BB) caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* and stem rot (SR) caused by *Sclerotium oryzae* are major diseases in nontraditional rice-growing areas of Haryana. We evaluated 30 promising rice cultivars for resistance during 1988 wet season.

To evaluate yield and yield-contributing characters, cultivars were transplanted in 6.2- × 2.0-m plots at 20- × 15-cm spacing in a randomized block design with three replications. The crop was

fertilized with 120 kg N, 26 kg P, and 5.75 kg Zn/ha. All the P and Zn were applied at puddling; N was applied in three equal splits: at transplanting, 21 d after transplanting (DT), and 42 DT.

To evaluate BB and SR resistance, cultivars were transplanted in two fields, in two 5-m-long rows/entry and an alternate row of susceptible check TN1 for BB and Jhona 349 for SR.

For BB screening, plants were clip-inoculated 45 DT by cutting 5 cm from the tip of the upper leaves with a sickle dipped in bacterial suspension (prepared by soaking small pieces of infected leaves 20 min). SR screening was done in an infected field.

Only six cultivars showed resistance to BB (see table). Seven entries showed resistance to SR.

Susceptibility of promising rice cultivars to BB and SR in Kaul, India, 1988 wet season.

Cultivar	Parentage	Yield (t/ha)	Grain type ^a	Reaction ^b to	
				Bacterial blight	Stem rot
IET8562	IET5122DR9168-13-2	4.9	MS	7	5
IET8950	RP270-36-1-2/Bankura 32	5.0	LS	7	5
IET9247	RPW6-17/ARC6650	5.0	LB	7	5
IET9552	RPW6-17PtB 2	4.1	LB	7	7
IET9553	RPW6-17PtB 2	4.1	LB	7	7
IET9557	RPW6-17PtB 2	4.4	LB	9	9
IET9686	RPW6-17/ARC6650	5.2	LS	7	7
IET9688	RPW6-17/ARC6650	5.1	LB	7	5
IET9700	RPW6-17/ARC6650	4.1	LB	7	1
IET9701	RPW6-17/ARC6650	4.6	LB	7	1
IET9910	ET4141/CR98-7216	5.1	LB	3	7
IET9912	IET4141/CR98-7216	5.4	SB	3	9
IET9924	IRS/Surekha	5.0	SB	7	9
IET9941	Sona/K118	4.4	LB	9	7
IET10294	IR20/CR95-1128	3.5	LS	5	3
IET10301	Phalguna/ARC6650	2.4	LB	7	5
IET10413	CR114/CR115	4.2	MS	3	1
IET10417	CR114/CR115	4.3	LS	5	1
IET10418	CR114/CR115	5.0	LS	3	3
IET10419	CR114/CR115	5.6	MS	7	5
IET10428	IR4219-35-3/IR4570	5.2	LS	7	3
IET10411	CR94/Ratna	5.0	MS	7	7
IET10312	CBII/Ratna	5.9	LS	3	5
IET10313	IR 162/Parmel	5.9	LS	3	7
IET10318	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	6.8	LS	7	5
IET10319	Nam Sagui 19/JR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	4.8	LS	7	9
IET10320	Nam Sagui 19/IR4215-301-2-2-6// IR5853-162-1-2-3	4.6	LS	7	9
IET10321	RP6-516-31-6Pusa 33	6.7	LB	5	7
Jaya (check)	RP6-516-31-6Pusa 33	5.5	LB	7	9
PR106 (check)	RP6-516-31-6Pusa 33	5.2	LS	7	7
LSD (0.05)		0.4			
CV (%)		4.9			

^a MS = medium slender, LS = long slender, LB = long bold, SB = short bold. ^b Resistant = with score of 3 or below, moderately resistant = score 5, susceptible = score 7 or above.

IET10413 and IET10418 showed resistance to both diseases, but their yields were less than those of the check varieties. IET10318 gave the highest yield, but it is susceptible to BB and only moderately resistant to SR. IET10321 also gave good grain yield, was moderately resistant to BB, and susceptible to SR. Entries IET10321 and IET10313 had good yields and showed resistance to BB. ■

Pest resistance - insects

Reaction of rice cultivars to rice hispa

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Hispa *Dicladispa armigera* (Oliv.) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) recently became a serious pest of rice, occurring in endemic form throughout Assam. Adult bugs scrape parenchymatous tissues off the rice leaves by making parallel streaks; grubs mine between the two epidermal layers inside the leaves. Damaged leaves dry up. Damaged rice plants look like straw. Heavy infestations can extensively damage winter, summer, and autumn rice.

We screened for resistance to hispa, 96 local cultivars suitable for postflood situations for resistance to hispa in early Sep 1987, 1988, and 1989 at Sensowapathar, an endemic area of Sibsagar.

The hispa population peaked (25-38 adults/hill) late Sep to early Oct. Borsali, the local susceptible check, had 100% infestation.

Reaction of rice cultivars to hispa in the field. Sibsagar, Assam, India, 1987-89.

Cultivar	Germplasm reference number	Leaf damage ^a (%)
Malbhog	NS 27	15
Pokikoli	NS 30	17
Silguti	S 307	17
Gajep sali-1	S 100	18
Sarusokua	S 248	20

^a Av of 1987, 1988, and 1989.

Local varieties Malbhog, Pokikoli, Silguti, Gajep sali 1, and Sarusokua suffered 15-20% leaf damage (see table). Nonpreference for feeding may be the resistance mechanism in these varieties. This study confirmed that glutinous rice varieties are less preferred by hispa. ■

Resistance of selected rice varieties to brown planthopper (BPH) and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

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The important rice pests in China—BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål and WBPH *Sogatellafurcifera* Horváth—usually occur together. Many varieties resistant to planthoppers have been released, and the threat of BPH and WBPH outbreaks significantly reduced. We evaluated damage, fecundity, and population dynamics of BPH and WBPH on some widely cultivated rice varieties, using the seedling screening technique in the glasshouse.

Xu-Shui 620 and Bing 664 were resistant to BPH but moderately resistant and moderately susceptible, respectively, to WBPH. Shan-You No. 6 was resistant to BPH but susceptible to WBPH. Both Shan-You 63 and Xiu-Shui 48 were susceptible to both BPH and WBPH.

In the ovipositing test, a pair of newly emerged BPH or WBPH adults were

Population dynamics of the brown planthopper (BPH) and the whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) on select on rice varieties in ricefields, Hangzhou, China, 1990.

introduced into test tubes containing one plant of a variety. Plants were replaced every 2 d and the number of eggs laid counted.

At tillering and booting, the BPH female laid significantly more eggs on Shan-You 63 and Xiu-Shui 48 than on other varieties, but BPH fecundity at booting was higher than at tillering (see table). Shan-You No. 6, Shan-You 63, and Xiu-Shui 48 received more WBPH eggs than Bing 664 and Xiu-Shui 620 at tillering, but at booting, significantly fewer WBPH eggs were laid on all varieties.

In a field survey, Xiu-Shui 620, Shan-You No. 6, and Bing 664 had lower BPH populations than Shan-You 63, and Xiu-Shui 48. The number of BPH increased gradually with plant age, but the number of WBPH decreased rapidly with plant

age after 73 d old. This seems to be due to the decline in fecundity of WBPH after booting (see figure).

Japonica variety Xiu-Shui 620 appears to be most valuable as a BPH and WBPH resistance donor. ■

Stress tolerance—adverse soils

Rice genotypes with tolerance for low available phosphorus in Sierra Leone soils

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Soils in Sierra Leone are low activity clay type and low in available P. Inadequate P retards growth and development of rice. Identification of genotypes tolerant of low available P will assist breeders and farmers in minimizing adverse effects of P deficiency.

In 1989-90, we screened 294 local rice collected in 1988 for tolerance for low available P. In the uplands, 72 accessions of *O. glaberrima* and 72 of *O. sativa* were tested with and without P; in the inland valley swamp, 70 accessions of *O. glaberrima* and 80 of *O. sativa* were evaluated.

Damage and fecundity of BPH and WBPH on selected rice varieties.^a Hangzhou, China, 1989.

Variety	Damage rating ^b		Fecundity of BPH ^c (eggs/female in 8 d)		Fecundity of WBPH ^c (eggs/female in 8 d)	
	BPH	WBPH	Tillering	Booting	Tillering	Booting
Shan-You No. 6	1.3	9.0	51.2 bc	79.2 b	112.7 ab	92.8 a
Shan-You 63	8.7	9.0	74.5 b	139.9 a	138.6 a	86.0 a
Xiu-Shui 620	1.0	3.7	56.0 bc	78.5 b	77.4 b	69.9 a
Bing 664	2.3	5.7	34.9 c	62.9 b	82.7 b	74.6 a
XU-Shui 48	9.0	8.0	128.9 a	132.0 a	126.5 a	93.0 a
Rathu Heenati (resistant check)	1.0	1.3	22.4 c	28.6 c	12.4 c	10.1 b
TN1 (susceptible check)	9.0	9.0	113.2 ab	125.6 a	104.8 ab	88.4 a

^aSeparation of means in a column by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level. ^bBy the Standard evaluation system for rice.

^cAv of 2 replications.